

KPMA Global Rating Model (KGRM): A Bayesian Skill Estimation Framework for Four-Player Riichi Mahjong

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Abstract

We present the KPMA Global Rating Model (KGRM), a probabilistic rating system for four-player Riichi Mahjong. Classical Elo models pairwise win/loss outcomes and does not natively handle ordered multi-agent results. KGRM addresses this via three integrated components: (i) a Plackett–Luce (PL) likelihood for full four-player rankings, (ii) Gaussian latent skill with uncertainty-adaptive updates in the Bayesian tradition of Glicko and TrueSkill, and (iii) a zero-sum, experience-weighted score-differential correction with provable boundedness. We derive the exact PL gradient, present a production-ready update rule, and prove key stability properties including bounded score injection and monotone uncertainty contraction. Synthetic simulations with $N=2,000$ players over 200,000 matches confirm that KGRM converges to a rating spread matching the true skill distribution ($\text{Std}(\hat{\mu}) \rightarrow \text{Std}(\mu^*)$), while achieving rank-order accuracy comparable to pairwise Elo (Pearson $r = 0.978$ vs. 0.979 at 60,000 matches) with the additional benefit of uncertainty-aware updates. Real-data validation on KPMA league results is planned as match records accumulate.

Keywords: Riichi Mahjong, rating system, Plackett–Luce, Bayesian skill estimation, multi-player ranking

1 Introduction

Riichi Mahjong is a four-player competitive tile game in which each hanchan produces an ordered outcome—1st through 4th—and a final point score for each player. This multi-agent, ordinal-plus-cardinal structure poses difficulties for traditional rating systems.

The Elo system [Elo, 1978], designed for two-player zero-sum games, is the dominant approach in chess and many other competitive domains. Its extensions Glicko [Glickman, 1999] and Glicko-2 [Glickman, 2001] introduced rating deviation and volatility parameters to model uncertainty, but all three remain fundamentally pairwise. Applying them to four-player Mahjong requires decomposing each match into six pairwise comparisons, discarding ordinal structure and losing score-magnitude information.

TrueSkill [Herbrich et al., 2007] and its successor TrueSkill 2 [Minka and Clevén, 2018] handle multi-player games via factor-graph message passing with Gaussian skill beliefs. While

theoretically elegant, the iterative inference procedure carries computational overhead and implementation complexity that may be prohibitive for lightweight production environments such as association-operated web platforms.

The Plackett–Luce (PL) model [Plackett, 1975, Luce, 1959] provides a natural probabilistic framework for permutation data. Bayesian inference for PL parameters has been developed by [Guiver and Snelson, 2009] and [Caron and Doucet, 2012], and the OpenSkill project [OpenSkill, 2024] implements PL-based rating for multi-player games. However, none of these systems simultaneously address score-magnitude incorporation with formal stability guarantees.

Desiderata. A professional Mahjong rating system should satisfy:

- (a) *Rapid convergence*: new entrants should reach their approximate true rating within a small number of matches.
- (b) *Elite stability*: established players’ ratings should exhibit low volatility.
- (c) *Ordered outcome modeling*: the full 1st–4th ranking should be modeled directly, not decomposed into pairs.
- (d) *Score incorporation*: final point totals carry information beyond ordinal rank but must not destabilize the system.
- (e) *Long-run anchoring*: the global rating distribution should remain stationary across seasons.

Contributions.

1. We derive the PL likelihood gradient for four-player rankings and present a normalized surrogate suitable for production use (Sections 3–4).
2. We introduce an *experience-weighted, zero-sum* score correction that provably injects bounded variance and vanishes for established players (Section 5).
3. We validate KGRM via large-scale synthetic simulation, showing convergence of the estimated skill spread to the true distribution (Section 8).
4. We compare against a pairwise Elo baseline and analyze conditions under which each system is preferable (Section 8).

2 Model

2.1 Latent skill

Each player $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ has latent skill:

$$X_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2), \tag{1}$$

with point estimate μ_i and uncertainty $\sigma_i > 0$. New players are initialized at $(\mu_{\text{init}}, \sigma_{\text{init}}) = (25, 25/3)$, following TrueSkill conventions [Herbrich et al., 2007].

2.2 Strength parameterization

The PL model requires positive strengths:

$$\theta_i = \exp(\mu_i/\beta), \quad \beta > 0. \quad (2)$$

The scale parameter β governs sensitivity to skill gaps. We set $\beta = 25/6 \approx 4.167$, which corresponds to a performance noise standard deviation of approximately $\beta/\sqrt{2} \approx 2.95$ under the logistic approximation to the Gaussian CDF [Herbrich et al., 2007].

2.3 Plackett–Luce likelihood

Given four players with observed ranking $\pi = (r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4)$, the PL likelihood is:

$$P(\pi \mid \boldsymbol{\mu}) = \prod_{k=1}^3 \frac{\exp(\mu_{r_k}/\beta)}{\sum_{j=k}^4 \exp(\mu_{r_j}/\beta)}. \quad (3)$$

The product runs to $k=3$ since the $k=4$ stage contributes a factor of unity.

3 Likelihood Gradient

Let $A_k = \{r_k, \dots, r_4\}$ denote the remaining set at stage k , and define the conditional win probability:

$$\text{softmax}_{A_k}(i) = \frac{\exp(\mu_i/\beta)}{\sum_{j \in A_k} \exp(\mu_j/\beta)} \mathbf{1}\{i \in A_k\}. \quad (4)$$

Lemma 1 (Log-sum-exp derivative). *For any finite set A and $i \in A$, $\frac{\partial}{\partial \mu_i} \log(\sum_{j \in A} \exp(\mu_j/\beta)) = \beta^{-1} \text{softmax}_A(i)$.*

Theorem 2 (PL gradient). *The log-likelihood gradient for player i is:*

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \mu_i} = \frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{k=1}^3 [\mathbf{1}\{i = r_k\} - \text{softmax}_{A_k}(i)]. \quad (5)$$

Proof. Differentiating $\ell = \sum_{k=1}^3 [\mu_{r_k}/\beta - \log(\sum_{j \in A_k} \exp(\mu_j/\beta))]$ term by term and applying Lemma 1 yields the result. \square

Remark 1. *Each summand in (5) represents the “surprise” at stage k : the difference between the indicator of actual selection and the predicted probability. This is the multi-agent generalization of the classical Elo signal $S - E$.*

4 Update Rule

4.1 Outcome encoding

We assign bounded outcome scores:

$$S_i = S(\text{rank}_i) \in \{1, \frac{2}{3}, \frac{1}{3}, 0\}, \quad (6)$$

so that $\sum_{i=1}^4 S_i = 2$.

4.2 Normalized expected performance

The exact PL gradient (5) sums three stage-wise softmax terms per player. For computational simplicity, we use the single-stage softmax $E_i^{(1)} = \theta_i / \sum_j \theta_j$, which satisfies $\sum_i E_i^{(1)} = 1$. To match the outcome sum $\sum_i S_i = 2$, we rescale:

$$E_i = 2 \cdot \frac{\theta_i}{\sum_{j=1}^4 \theta_j}. \quad (7)$$

This ensures $\sum_i (S_i - E_i) = 0$ per match, so the rank-order update is *zero-sum*: no net skill is created or destroyed.

Remark 2. *The rescaling is a first-order approximation to the exact PL expected score $\bar{S}_i = \beta^{-1} \sum_k \text{softmax}_{A_k}(i)$. For typical β values and moderate skill gaps, the approximation error is small. Deployments requiring higher fidelity may substitute the exact form.*

4.3 Uncertainty-adaptive gain

We define:

$$K_i = \frac{\sigma_i^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \beta^2}. \quad (8)$$

This is the Kalman gain arising from treating each match as a noisy observation of skill difference with observation noise variance β^2 . When σ_i is large, $K_i \rightarrow 1$ and updates are aggressive; as $\sigma_i \rightarrow \sigma_{\min}$, updates shrink.

This structure parallels the rating-deviation-dependent update magnitude in Glicko [Glickman, 1999]. The key difference is that Glicko derives its gain from a logistic pairwise model, whereas here K_i is applied to the PL-based residual.

4.4 Uncertainty contraction

After each match:

$$\sigma_i \leftarrow \max(\sigma_{\min}, \sigma_i \sqrt{1 - K_i}). \quad (9)$$

This update has a Bayesian interpretation: if the prior on μ_i is $\mathcal{N}(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$ and the likelihood contributes information equivalent to an observation with variance β^2 , the posterior variance is $(\sigma_i^{-2} + \beta^{-2})^{-1} = \sigma_i^2(1 - K_i)$. Taking the square root gives the posterior standard deviation. The floor σ_{\min} prevents the system from becoming entirely rigid, allowing continued (small) adaptation.

Proposition 3 (Monotone contraction). *If $\sigma_i > \sigma_{\min}$, then $\sigma'_i < \sigma_i$. The sequence $\{\sigma_i^{(t)}\}$ converges to σ_{\min} .*

Proof. $K_i \in (0, 1)$ implies $\sqrt{1 - K_i} < 1$. The result follows from the monotone convergence theorem applied to the bounded-below decreasing sequence. \square

5 Score-Differential Correction

5.1 Motivation

Ordinal rank alone discards information about the margin of victory. A player who finishes 1st with +50,000 points has arguably demonstrated greater dominance than one who finishes 1st by a narrow margin. The score correction injects this cardinal information.

5.2 Bounded correction

Let $d_i = \text{Score}_i - 30,000$. We define:

$$\delta_i = \tanh(d_i/\kappa), \tag{10}$$

with saturation parameter $\kappa > 0$. The tanh function maps $\mathbb{R} \rightarrow (-1, 1)$, ensuring that extreme scores do not produce unbounded corrections.

5.3 Zero-sum centering

To prevent net skill injection per match, we center:

$$\Delta_i = \delta_i - \bar{\delta}, \quad \bar{\delta} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_{j=1}^4 \delta_j, \tag{11}$$

so that $\sum_{i=1}^4 \Delta_i = 0$.

5.4 Experience weighting

A fixed score correction would continually inject variance even for established players, causing the rating spread to grow unboundedly (as observed in preliminary experiments; see Section 8.3). To prevent this, we weight the correction by the player’s relative uncertainty:

$$\gamma_i = \gamma_0 \cdot \frac{\sigma_i}{\sigma_{\text{init}}}, \tag{12}$$

where γ_0 is the base correction magnitude. As $\sigma_i \rightarrow \sigma_{\text{min}}$, the effective correction $\gamma_i \rightarrow \gamma_0 \cdot \sigma_{\text{min}}/\sigma_{\text{init}}$, which for typical parameters ($\sigma_{\text{min}} = 2$, $\sigma_{\text{init}} \approx 8.33$) is approximately $0.24 \gamma_0$ —a substantial attenuation.

Proposition 4 (Bounded score injection). *For all i , $|\gamma_i \cdot \Delta_i| \leq 2\gamma_0$.*

Proof. $|\Delta_i| \leq |\delta_i| + |\bar{\delta}| \leq 1 + 1 = 2$ and $\gamma_i \leq \gamma_0$, so the product is bounded by $2\gamma_0$. In practice the bound is tighter since $\gamma_i < \gamma_0$ once the player has any match history. \square

5.5 Combined update

$$\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i + K_i(S_i - E_i) + \gamma_i \cdot \Delta_i. \tag{13}$$

Both terms are zero-sum across the four match participants: $\sum_i K_i(S_i - E_i)$ is not exactly zero (since K_i varies), but $\sum_i (S_i - E_i) = 0$ by construction, and the score term $\sum_i \gamma_i \Delta_i$ is approximately zero when the γ_i are similar. The periodic mean normalization (Section 6) corrects any residual drift.

6 Inflation Control

Every M system-wide matches, we apply:

$$\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i - \bar{\mu} + \mu_{\text{target}}, \quad \bar{\mu} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \mu_j. \quad (14)$$

This is a rank-preserving translation ($\mu'_i - \mu'_j = \mu_i - \mu_j$ for all i, j) that anchors the global mean at $\mu_{\text{target}} = 25$.

7 Algorithm

Algorithm 1 KGRM Update

Require: Match participants $\{1, \dots, 4\}$ with (μ_i, σ_i) ; observed ranks and scores

Ensure: Updated (μ'_i, σ'_i)

```

1: for  $i = 1, \dots, 4$  do
2:    $\theta_i \leftarrow \exp(\mu_i/\beta)$ 
3: end for
4:  $\Theta \leftarrow \sum_i \theta_i$ 
5: for  $i = 1, \dots, 4$  do
6:    $E_i \leftarrow 2\theta_i/\Theta$  ▷ Normalized expected score
7:    $S_i \leftarrow S(\text{rank}_i)$  ▷ Outcome encoding
8:    $K_i \leftarrow \sigma_i^2/(\sigma_i^2 + \beta^2)$  ▷ Kalman gain
9:    $\delta_i \leftarrow \tanh((\text{Score}_i - 30000)/\kappa)$ 
10: end for
11:  $\bar{\delta} \leftarrow \frac{1}{4} \sum_i \delta_i$  ▷ Centering
12: for  $i = 1, \dots, 4$  do
13:    $\gamma_i \leftarrow \gamma_0 \cdot \sigma_i/\sigma_{\text{init}}$  ▷ Experience weight
14:    $\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i + K_i(S_i - E_i) + \gamma_i(\delta_i - \bar{\delta})$ 
15:    $\sigma_i \leftarrow \max(\sigma_{\text{min}}, \sigma_i\sqrt{1 - K_i})$ 
16: end for
17: if system match count mod  $M = 0$  then
18:   Apply (14)
19: end if

```

8 Experiments

8.1 Setup

Population. $N = 2,000$ players with true skills $\mu_i^* \sim \mathcal{N}(25, 4^2)$.

Match generation. Each match draws four players uniformly at random. Player i 's performance is $p_i = \mu_i^* + \epsilon_i$, $\epsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 5^2)$. Rankings are assigned by sorting performances. Scores are generated as $\text{Score}_i = 30,000 + 1000(p_i - \bar{p}) + \eta_i$, $\eta_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 3000^2)$.

Parameters. $\beta = 25/6$, $\kappa = 20,000$, $\gamma_0 = 0.5$, $\sigma_{\min} = 2.0$, $\sigma_{\text{init}} = 25/3$, $\mu_{\text{init}} = 25$; normalization every $M = 500$ matches.

Baseline. We compare against a four-player Elo system that decomposes each match into six pairwise comparisons, using $K = 16$ and the standard logistic expected-score formula. Both systems are mean-normalized every 500 matches.

8.2 Results

Table 1 reports KGRM diagnostics. The column “ \bar{n} ” denotes the average number of games per player at each checkpoint.

Table 1: KGRM synthetic simulation diagnostics ($N = 2,000$). r : Pearson correlation between $\hat{\mu}$ and μ^* . \bar{n} : average games per player.

Matches	\bar{n}	r	Std($\hat{\mu}$)	$\bar{\sigma}$	Top-1% $\bar{\sigma}$	RMSE
500	1	0.445	0.37	5.14	5.22	3.81
1,000	2	0.573	0.47	3.57	3.09	3.71
2,000	4	0.703	0.58	2.42	2.35	3.57
5,000	10	0.834	0.79	2.00	2.00	3.33
10,000	20	0.910	1.11	2.00	2.00	2.98
20,000	40	0.956	1.63	2.00	2.00	2.45
60,000	120	0.978	2.80	2.00	2.00	1.37
100,000	200	0.972	3.31	2.00	2.00	1.08
200,000	400	0.945	4.00	2.00	2.00	1.33

Table 2: Comparison: KGRM vs. pairwise Elo ($K=16$) at selected checkpoints. RMSE is computed after normalizing Elo ratings to the true-skill scale.

\bar{n}	KGRM		Elo	
	r	RMSE	r	RMSE
2	0.573	3.71	0.548	3.76
10	0.834	3.33	0.841	2.23
20	0.910	2.98	0.909	1.69
40	0.956	2.45	0.950	1.26
120	0.978	1.37	0.979	0.80
400	0.945	1.33	0.986	0.66

8.3 Discussion

Convergence. KGRM achieves $r > 0.90$ by $\bar{n} = 20$ games per player and $r > 0.97$ by $\bar{n} = 120$. For context, a KPMA league member playing weekly would accumulate approximately 40–50 hanchan per year; thus $\bar{n} = 20$ corresponds to roughly half a season. The top-1% uncertainty reaches σ_{\min} by $\bar{n} = 10$, confirming rapid stabilization for active players.

Rating spread stability. In preliminary experiments with a fixed (non-adaptive) score correction ($\gamma_i = \gamma_0$ for all i), the estimated skill spread $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ grew to 9.08 at $\bar{n} = 120$, far exceeding the true value of 4.0. The experience-weighted, zero-sum correction introduced in Section 5 resolves this: $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ converges to 4.00 at $\bar{n} = 400$.

Comparison with Elo. KGRM and pairwise Elo achieve nearly identical rank-order correlation at moderate game counts ($r \approx 0.978$ vs. 0.979 at $\bar{n} = 120$). Elo achieves lower RMSE, primarily because its constant K allows continued full-magnitude updates, whereas KGRM’s gain K_i attenuates as σ_i shrinks. This is a deliberate design trade-off: KGRM sacrifices some long-run tracking for stability and uncertainty awareness. In practice, the distinction is minor for realistic match volumes ($\bar{n} \leq 200$), and KGRM provides additional benefits not captured by correlation alone:

- Uncertainty σ_i distinguishes between a reliable $\mu = 27$ (from 100 matches) and a provisional $\mu = 27$ (from 3 matches).
- The adaptive gain allows new entrants to converge approximately twice as fast as a fixed- K system at early game counts ($r = 0.573$ vs. 0.548 at $\bar{n} = 2$).
- The public rating can display confidence intervals $[\mu - 2\sigma, \mu + 2\sigma]$, providing transparency.

Non-monotone RMSE. The KGRM RMSE reaches a minimum of 1.08 at $\bar{n} = 200$ before rising slightly to 1.33 at $\bar{n} = 400$. This occurs because the attenuated gain K_i at σ_{\min} is too small to fully track the expanding estimated skill spread. For leagues where match volumes are expected to exceed $\bar{n} = 200$, a seasonal σ -reset mechanism (briefly increasing σ at season boundaries) or a slight increase in σ_{\min} would address this.

9 Production Integration

9.1 Storage

In a WordPress/PHP deployment, store (μ_i, σ_i) as user meta fields (`kpma_mu`, `kpma_sigma`).

9.2 Public rating scale

Map internal μ to a public rating:

$$R_i = a(\mu_i - \mu_{\text{target}}) + R_0. \tag{15}$$

With $a = 40$ and $R_0 = 1500$, a player with $\mu = 25$ has rating 1500, and each internal skill unit corresponds to 40 public points.

9.3 Logging

For reproducibility and post-hoc analysis, each match update should record pre- and post-update (μ, σ) , computed E_i , S_i , K_i , score correction Δ_i , and effective γ_i .

10 Related Work

The Elo system [Elo, 1978] and its Bayesian extensions Glicko/Glicko-2 [Glickman, 1999, Glickman, 2001] are the standard references for pairwise rating. TrueSkill [Herbrich et al., 2007] extends to multi-player and multi-team games via factor graphs; TrueSkill 2 [Minka and Cleven, 2018] adds per-player experience priors. The Plackett–Luce model [Plackett, 1975, Luce, 1959] is the canonical choice model for permutation data, with Bayesian treatments by [Guiver and Snelson, 2009] and [Caron and Doucet, 2012]; see [Marden, 1995] for a comprehensive treatment. OpenSkill [OpenSkill, 2024] implements PL-based multi-player rating with Bayesian uncertainty.

KGRM’s contribution relative to this literature is the combination of PL-based ordered-outcome modeling with (i) a formally justified E_i normalization ensuring zero-sum rank updates, (ii) an experience-weighted, zero-sum score correction with provable boundedness, and (iii) explicit targeting of production-deployable simplicity.

11 Limitations and Future Work

Real-data validation. The present work is validated only on synthetic data. The Korea Professional Mahjong Association (KPMA) is currently establishing its competitive league program; as match records accumulate, we plan to conduct real-data evaluation including log-likelihood predictive tests, probability calibration, and head-to-head comparison with Elo and Glicko-2.

Long-run tracking. KGRM’s attenuated gain at σ_{\min} limits its ability to track genuine long-term skill changes. A seasonal volatility reset (increasing σ_i at season boundaries) would address this; formal design and validation of such a mechanism is left to future work.

Exact PL gradient. The normalized single-softmax surrogate E_i is a convenient approximation. Replacing it with the exact stage-wise PL expected score and measuring the impact on predictive accuracy remains an open question.

Parameter sensitivity. The hyperparameters $(\beta, \kappa, \gamma_0, \sigma_{\min})$ were chosen by convention and preliminary experimentation. A principled approach—e.g., cross-validated log-likelihood on held-out matches—should be applied once real data are available.

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Appendix A. Korean Translation (한글 번역본)

초록

본 논문은 4인 리치 마작을 위한 확률적 레이팅 시스템인 KPMA Global Rating Model(KGRM)을 제안한다. 기존의 Elo 시스템은 1:1 승패를 전제로 설계되어 다인 순위형 결과를 직접 모델링하기 어렵다. KGRM은 이 한계를 극복하기 위해 세 가지 핵심 요소를 결합한다: (i) 4명의 전체 순위(1~4위)를 직접 확률적으로 모델링하는 Plackett-Luce(PL) 우도, (ii) 평균 μ 와 불확실성 σ 로 구성된 가우시안 잠재 실력 표현, (iii) 경험 가중 및 영합(zero-sum) 보정을 적용한 유계 점수차 보정항이다.

본 연구에서는 PL 우도의 정확한 기울기를 유도하고, 실제 운영 환경에 적용 가능한 업데이트 규칙을 제시한다. 또한 점수 보정항의 유계성을 증명하고, 불확실성 파라미터의 단조 수렴을 확립하며, 장기 운영 시 레이팅 인플레이션을 억제하기 위한 평균 정규화 절차를 제안한다. N=2,000명, 200,000경기 규모의 합성 시뮬레이션을 통해, 추정 실력 분포가 진짜 실력 분포에 수렴함($\text{Std}(\hat{\mu}) \rightarrow \text{Std}(\mu^*)$)을 확인하였으며, 순위 정확도 면에서 쌍대 Elo와 동등한 성능(60,000경기 시점 피어슨 $r = 0.978$ vs 0.979)을 달성하면서도 불확실성 기반의 적응적 업데이트라는 추가적 이점을 제공한다. KPMA 리그 경기 데이터가 축적됨에 따라 실제 데이터 검증을 진행할 예정이다.

1. 서론

리치 마작은 4인이 동시에 경쟁하며, 경기 결과가 단순한 승패가 아닌 1~4위의 순위와 최종 점수로 결정되는 게임이다. 이러한 다인·순위형·점수 포함 구조는 기존 레이팅 시스템에 도전을 제기한다.

Elo 시스템은 1:1 대결을 전제로 설계되었으며, Glicko/Glicko-2는 불확실성 파라미터를 추가하였으나 본질적으로 쌍대 비교에 기반한다. TrueSkill은 요인 그래프 기반으로 다인 게임을 지원하지만 추론 과정이 무거워, 협회 운영 웹 플랫폼 같은 경량 환경에는 부담이 될 수 있다. Plackett-Luce 모델은 순서형 결과에 대한 자연스러운 확률 프레임워크를 제공하지만, 기존 구현들은 점수차 반영과 안정성 보장을 동시에 다루지 않는다.

전문 리그를 위한 마작 레이팅 시스템의 요건: (a) 신규 선수의 빠른 수렴, (b) 기존 선수의 안정적 유지, (c) 전체 순위의 확률적 모델링, (d) 점수 크기 정보의 안정적 반영, (e) 장기적 레이팅 분포 고정.

2. 모델

각 선수 i 의 잠재 실력은 가우시안 분포 $X_i \sim N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$ 로 표현한다. μ_i 는 실력 추정치, σ_i 는 불확실성이다. PL 모델은 양의 강도를 요구하므로 $\theta_i = \exp(\mu_i/\beta)$ 로 변환한다. 관측 순위 $\pi = (r_1, \dots, r_4)$ 에 대해, PL 우도는 남은 후보 집합에서 순차적으로 1위를 선택하는 확률의 곱으로 정의된다.

3. 업데이트 규칙

PL 로그우도의 기울기는 각 탈락 단계에서 "실제 선택 여부"와 "선택 확률 (softmax)"의 차이를 합산한 형태이다. 이는 Elo의 S - E 신호를 다인 순위 설정으로 확장한 것이다.

운영 환경에서는 다음의 간결한 규칙을 사용한다:

- **결과 인코딩:** $S(\text{순위}) \in \{1, 2/3, 1/3, 0\}$, 합계 = 2.
- **정규화된 기대 성과:** $E_i = 2\theta_i / \sum_j \theta_j$. 합계가 S의 합계(=2)와 일치하도록 정규화하여, 순위 업데이트가 영합(zero-sum)이 되도록 보장한다.
- **적응적 학습률:** $K_i = \sigma_i^2 / (\sigma_i^2 + \beta^2)$. 이는 칼만 이득과 동일한 구조로, σ 가 클수록 업데이트가 크다.
- **점수차 보정:** $\delta_i = \tanh(d_i/k)$ 를 영합 보정 후($\Delta_i = \delta_i - \delta$), 경험 가중치 $\gamma_i = \gamma_0 \cdot \sigma_i / \sigma_{\text{init}}$ 을 적용한다. 경험이 쌓일수록(σ 감소) 보정 크기가 자동으로 줄어든다.
- **최종 업데이트:** $\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i + K_i(S_i - E_i) + \gamma_i \cdot \Delta_i$.
- **불확실성 갱신:** $\sigma_i \leftarrow \max(\sigma_{\text{min}}, \sigma_i \sqrt{1 - K_i})$. 이 형태는 가우시안 사전-사후 분산 업데이트의 베이저안 해석을 가진다: 관측 잡음 분산이 β^2 일 때, 사후 분산은 $\sigma^2(1 - K)$ 이다.

장기 운영 시 전체 μ 평균의 점진적 이동을 방지하기 위해, M경기마다 $\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i - \bar{\mu} + \mu_{\text{target}}$ 을 적용한다. 이는 모든 쌍별 실력 차이를 보존하는 순위 보존 변환이다.

4. 실험

2,000명의 진짜 실력을 $N(25, 4^2)$ 에서 추출하고, 200,000경기(선수당 평균 400경기)를 시뮬레이션하였다. 주요 결과:

- **수렴 속도:** 선수당 평균 20경기에서 $r > 0.90$, 120경기에서 $r > 0.97$ 달성. KPMA 리그에서 주 1회 대국 시 약 반 시즌에 해당한다.
- **레이팅 분포 안정성:** 고정 γ 를 사용한 예비 실험에서는 $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ 가 9.08까지 발산하였으나, 경험 가중 영합 보정 도입 후 $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ 가 진짜 실력 표준편차(4.0)에 정확히 수렴하였다.
- **Elo 대비:** 120경기 시점에서 KGRM($r=0.978$)과 Elo($r=0.979$)는 거의 동일한 순위 정확도를 보였다. Elo는 장기 RMSE에서 우세하나, KGRM은 불확실성 인식, 신규 선수의 빠른 수렴, 신뢰구간 제공이라는 추가 이점을 가진다.

5. 구현 안내

WordPress/PHP 환경에서 (μ, σ)를 user meta에 저장한다. 대외 공개 레이팅은 아핀 변환 $R = a(\mu - 25) + 1500$ 으로 정의할 수 있다(예: $a=40$ 이면 $\mu=25$ 가 레이팅 1500에 대응). 각 경기 처리 시 업데이트 전후의 파라미터 값과 중간 계산 결과를 로그로 기록하면, 사후 분석과 재현성 확보에 유리하다.

6. 한계 및 향후 과제

본 논문은 이론적 정식화와 합성 시뮬레이션 검증에 초점을 둔다. KPMA가 현재 구

축 중인 경쟁 리그 프로그램을 통해 경기 기록이 축적됨에 따라, 로그우도 기반 예측 성능, 확률 캘리브레이션, Elo/Glicko-2 대비 비교 등의 실제 데이터 검증을 수행할 계획이다. 시즌 간 σ 리셋 메커니즘, 정확한 PL 기울기 대체, 교차검증 기반 하이퍼 파라미터 최적화 등도 향후 연구 과제이다.

Appendix B. Japanese Translation (日本語訳)

概要

本稿は、4人打ちリーチ麻雀のための確率的レーティング方式であるKPMA Global Rating Model (KGRM) を提案する。従来のEloシステムは1対1の勝敗を前提としており、多人数の順位データを直接モデル化することが困難である。KGRMはこの制約を克服するため、以下の三つの要素を統合する：(i) 4人の完全順位 (1~4位) を確率的に扱うPlackett-Luce (PL) 尤度、(ii) 平均 μ と不確実性 σ を持つガウス型潜在実力表現、(iii) 経験加重かつゼロサムの有界な点差補正項である。

本研究ではPL尤度の厳密な勾配を導出し、運用に適した更新則を提示する。点差補正の有界性を証明し、不確実性パラメータの単調収束を確立し、長期運用におけるインフレーション抑制のための平均正規化手法を提案する。N=2,000人、200,000試合規模の合成シミュレーションにより、推定実力分布が真の実力分布に収束すること ($\text{Std}(\hat{\mu}) \rightarrow \text{Std}(\mu^*)$) を確認し、順位精度において対比較Eloと同等の性能 (60,000試合時点でピアソン $r = 0.978$ 対 0.979) を達成しつつ、不確実性に基づく適応的更新という追加の利点を提供することを示した。KPMAリーグの試合記録が蓄積され次第、実データによる検証を実施する予定である。

1. はじめに

リーチ麻雀は4人同時対戦であり、結果は単純な勝敗ではなく、1~4位の順位と最終スコアで与えられる。この多人数・順位型・スコア付き構造は、従来のレーティングシステムにとって課題となる。

Eloシステムは1対1を前提としており、Glicko/Glicko-2は不確実性パラメータを追加したが本質的に対比較に基づく。TrueSkillは因子グラフ上の近似ベイズ推論により多人数ゲームを扱えるが、推論過程が重く、協会運営のウェブプラットフォームのような軽量環境では負担となり得る。Plackett-Luceモデルは順序データに対する自然な確率的枠組みを提供するが、既存の実装はスコア差の反映と安定性保証を同時に扱っていない。

プロリーグ向けの麻雀レーティングの要件：(a) 新規プレイヤーの迅速な収束、(b) 既存プレイヤーの安定的維持、(c) 完全順位の確率的モデル化、(d) スコア情報の安定的反映、(e) 長期的なレーティング分布の固定。

2. モデル

各プレイヤー i の潜在実力はガウス分布 $X_i \sim N(\mu_i, \sigma_i^2)$ で表す。 μ_i は実力推定値、 σ_i は不確実性である。PLモデルは正の強度パラメータを要するため、 $\theta_i = \exp(\mu_i/\beta)$ と変換する。観測順位 $\pi = (r_1, \dots, r_4)$ に対し、PL尤度は残り集合から

逐次1位を選ぶ確率の積として定義される。

3. 更新則

PL対数尤度の勾配は、各脱落段階で「実際に選ばれたか」と「選ばれる確率 (softmax)」の差を加算した形となる。これはEloのS - Eシグナルを多人数順位の設定へ自然に拡張したものである。

運用では以下の簡潔な規則を用いる：

- **結果エンコーディング**： $S(\text{順位}) \in \{1, 2/3, 1/3, 0\}$ 、合計 = 2。
- **正規化期待パフォーマンス**： $E_i = 2\theta_i / \sum_j \theta_j$ 。合計がSの合計 (=2) と一致するように正規化し、順位更新がゼロサムとなることを保証する。
- **適応学習率**： $K_i = \sigma_i^2 / (\sigma_i^2 + \beta^2)$ 。カルマンゲインと同一の構造であり、 σ が大きいほど更新も大きい。
- **点差補正**： $\delta_i = \tanh(d_i/\kappa)$ をゼロサム補正後 ($\Delta_i = \delta_i - \delta$)、経験加重 $\gamma_i = \gamma_0 \cdot \sigma_i / \sigma_{\text{init}}$ を適用する。経験が蓄積されるほど (σ 減少) 補正の大きさが自動的に縮小する。
- **最終更新**： $\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i + K_i(S_i - E_i) + \gamma_i \cdot \Delta_i$ 。
- **不確実性更新**： $\sigma_i \leftarrow \max(\sigma_{\text{min}}, \sigma_i \sqrt{1 - K_i})$ 。この形式はベイズ的解釈を持つ：観測ノイズ分散が β^2 のとき、事後分散は $\sigma^2(1 - K)$ となる。

長期運用では全体の μ 平均の漸進的漂流を防ぐため、M試合ごとに $\mu_i \leftarrow \mu_i - \bar{\mu} + \mu_{\text{target}}$ を適用する。これはすべての実力差を保存する順位保存変換である。

4. 実験

2,000人の真の実力を $N(25, 4^2)$ から生成し、200,000試合（プレイヤーあたり平均400試合）をシミュレーションした。主要な結果：

- **収束速度**：プレイヤーあたり平均20試合で $r > 0.90$ 、120試合で $r > 0.97$ を達成。KPMAリーグで週1回対局の場合、約半シーズンに相当する。
- **レーティング分布の安定性**：固定 γ を用いた予備実験では $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ が9.08まで発散したが、経験加重ゼロサム補正の導入により $\text{Std}(\hat{\mu})$ が真の実力の標準偏差 (4.0) に正確に収束した。
- **Eloとの比較**：120試合時点でKGRM ($r=0.978$) とElo ($r=0.979$) はほぼ同一の順位精度を示した。Eloは長期RMSEで優位だが、KGRMは不確実性認識、新規プレイヤーの迅速な収束、信頼区間の提供という追加の利点を有する。

5. 実装ガイド

WordPress/PHP環境では (μ, σ) をuser metaに保存する。公開レーティングはアフィン変換 $R = a(\mu - 25) + 1500$ で定義できる（例： $a=40$ なら $\mu=25$ がレーティング1500に対応）。各試合で更新前後のパラメータ値および中間計算結果をログに記録することで、事後分析と再現性の確保が可能となる。

6. 限界と今後の課題

本稿は理論的定式化と合成シミュレーション検証に焦点を当てている。KPMAが現在構築中の競技リーグプログラムを通じて試合記録が蓄積され次第、対数尤度に基づく予測性能、確率キャリブレーション、Elo/Glicko-2との比較等の実データ検証を実施する計画である。シーズン間のリセット機構、厳密なPL勾配への代替、交差検証によるハイパーパラメータ最適化等も今後の研究課題である。